

ParCare Community Health Network

Providing primary care, internal medicine, dermatology, physical therapy, occupational therapy, speech therapy, pediatrics, obstetrics, and other specialties, ParCare Community Health Network is a [multi-specialty center](#) with six locations.

In the past decade, residential development in the New Williamsburg neighborhood and surrounding areas has boomed, but health care services have not been developed at the same rate.

Thus, residents of this new community and their surrounding areas suffered from significant health care disparities and lack of access. This is how ParCare Community Health Network came to be.

ParCare Community Health Network strives to expand the mission of high quality clinical services and to serve those most in need. Parcare Community Health Network is a Not-for-profit New York State Article 28 Diagnostic and Treatment Center.

ParCare Community Health Network is a [community-based health center](#) that provides primary and specialty healthcare, helping our patients prevent disease and maintain good health. The center offers affordable, accessible, comprehensive medical services to thousands of otherwise underserved patients.

ParCare Community Health Network's mission is to provide quality health care to the community that we have the privilege of serving, while also being a great employer for our employees.

We focus on compassion, integrity, and accountability at ParCare Community Health Network. Every patient receives the highest quality of care and we focus on a holistic approach that caters to their needs.

A dedicated and compassionate team of professionals from a variety of cultural backgrounds is committed to providing our outpatient population with the best possible primary and preventative health care.

All those who might not otherwise be able to afford medical care are served by [ParCare Community Health Network](#). Our practice accepts most commercial insurance plans, Medicare and Medicaid HMOs such as HealthFirst, HealthPlus, Americhoice, All UHC plans, etc.